

MANUAL FEATURES OF WORDS DENOTING A SIGN IN THE CATEGORY OF ADJECTIVES

Irgasheva Dilnoza Makhsudjonovna

Samarkand Medical University

Lecturer of the Department of “Uzbek language and Literature with Russian”

Annotation: Usually adjectives form word combinations with nouns or pronouns of the matching type, i.e. one word in such a phrase is the main one and defines the grammatical categories of the second word, therefore all grammatical categories of adjectives depend on the grammatical categories of nouns or pronouns. Adjectives can be defined by grammatical gender (masculine, feminine, neuter), number (singular, plural), case, as well as the degree of comparison – a category that is typical for adjectives and adverbs.

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The grammatical dependence of adjectives on nouns is complete (see the examples above), which means that adjectives agree with nouns in gender, number and case, however, in the plural, generic differences are erased and only two endings are possible for all adjectives: new houses/rooms/seas, large houses/rooms/seas, blue houses/rooms/seas.

In modern Russian, in addition to declinable adjectives, there are also non-declinable adjectives (or in other words, adjectives without morphological characteristics), which include words like Bordeaux, beige; flash (we are talking mainly about loanwords).

Adjectives are most often formed using the suffixes method (glass, wooden, rainy, children's) (стеклянный, деревянный, дождливый, детский), prefixed (ultramodern, unsanitary, polar, beautiful) or suffixed-prefixed (school, seaside, table). New adjectives are also formed by addition (railway, Russian, light brown),

a non-morphological combination of two words: the signatories below = the undersigned, the above address = the above, or the so-called adjectivation (the transition of participles into adjectives), for example. Outstanding achievements, laughing eyes. From a syntactic point of view, adjectives usually perform the function of defining either the nominal part of the predicate.

Relative adjectives, unlike qualitative ones, denote a constant, unchanging feature, so these adjectives do not have degrees of comparison. Relative adjectives denote a feature through the relation of a given subject (person) to other subjects, signs, conditions, e.g. a student dormitory (= "dormitory for students"), a reading room (= "reading room / where you can read"), a morning newspaper (= "newspaper that came out / comes out in the morning").

Most relative adjectives are formed from nouns, hence the meaning of relative adjectives – "the designation of a feature through the relation of a given object (person) to other objects, signs, conditions": seaport (the sea is formed using the suffix -sk-), an eye doctor, a wooden table, silver dishes, a plastic window (глазной врач, деревянный стол, серебряная посуда, пластиковое окно).

As for the commonality between adjectives in Uzbek and Russian, they are a set of words denoting a subject in both languages. In both Uzbek and Russian, adjectives are syntactically related to nouns and usually act as a determinant or shorten speech. By the nature of the sign, adjectives are divided into initial and relative ones. In both languages, qualitative adjectives represent a fixed sign of an object. Such adjectives are hierarchical in both languages, and relative adjectives do not belong to the category of degree.

However, there are more general differences between Uzbek and Russian adjectives, which can be seen in the following: Uzbek primitive adjectives do not have a special morphological feature;

Russian adjectives, like nouns, have special endings denoting gender, number and agreement, and these endings are expressed in the process of subordination of

the noun to the adjective: if the name is a masculine noun, then the adjective gets the ending - th, if feminine nouns, in the middle gender is -her, in the plural - s, -ie. These endings are visible even in adjectives.

We chose the adjective rich/rich as the object of research due to the fact that this concept is very common and productive in the languages under study. The high frequency of its use in speech communication makes it possible to classify it into the category of words included in the dictionary-the minimum of everyone who speaks these languages. Rich, poor are words with collapsed propositional semantics, "featured names". Such adjectives express the concept of a feature that is characteristic of both persons and objects, phenomena and states. In this regard, the semantic structures of these adjectives are of considerable interest for studying the issues of ambiguity. There is no data on what meanings and under what conditions these words are used. In our opinion, such adjectives provide a rich and diverse material for studying ways to implement their meanings.

The external criterion for distinguishing the meanings of an adjective in combinations is the lexical and semantic characteristic of a noun, that is, a more detailed semantic characteristic based on its belonging to a certain lexical series. This may include animate nouns, inanimate nouns, and names of various objects. In all cases of description, it is important to rely on the speech context, since the analyzed adjectives can appear in different meanings. The most numerous analyzed adjectives are in the colloquial style of both languages.

Adjectives with the concept of "rich" in the studied languages are numerous in the predicative function. They are often repeated in speech communication. They are most productive in predicative function in comparative and superlative degrees. The forms of use of these adjectives can be different. They form word-formation nests. The word-formation nests of the adjectives rich "rich" are relatively equivalent: affixation, word composition, and substantiation are represented in both word-formation nests. All the adjectives with the meaning "rich" are included in this

semantic concept, have many synonymous variants, among which rich is the dominant one. Its various meanings can be used here, in which such lexemes as very, quite, enough, more, less appear.

Qualitative adjectives are combined with nouns denoting a person (person) and not a person (animals, objects, plants). The LSG of adjectives denoting the size of an object includes lexical and semantic variants of adjectives of linear (long coat, thick shell, narrow trousers, low town, etc.) and cumulative size (large drill, huge lime trees, gigantic samovar, etc.). Adjectives denoting the total size of an object can be depicted as a scale of gradations representing the increase / decrease in the degree of a feature: gigantic — gigantic — colossal — great — huge — decent — extensive - large <norm> small (small) — small - tiny. The average element denoting the norm (the value of the usual (average) size) was not found in the poem.

The graded semantics of qualitative adjectives in modern Russian can be represented explicitly and implicitly. The means of explicit expression of the semantics of graduality is the use of forms with more/less and most (analytical form) and the suffixes of the comparative and superlative: When the clerk said: "It would be nice, master, to do this and that," - "Yes, it's not bad," he usually answered, smoking a pipe, which he made a habit of smoking when he was still serving in the army, where he was considered the most modest, most delicate and educated officer // lexemes the most modest, most delicate and educated They have an relative meaning of "very modest", "very delicate", "very educated". The implicit way of expressing graded semantics includes qualitative adjectives forming graded oppositions: singleton (silver), two-element (straight - XX — oblique (direction), thick — sparse — liquid (hair)), three—element (old - medium — young), four—element (hot - warm — cool — cold) and multi-element sets (. — huge — large - medium—sized -small - small - .). The use of qualitative adjectives in N.V. Gogol's poem "Dead Souls" is productive, but they are quite diverse. Most of the linguistic units are clearly divided into lexical and semantic groups and analyzed, but a

separate part of the adjectives remained outside the scope of the study due to their semantic complexity, syncretism or limitations.

The results of comparative linguistics are the empirical material of linguistic typology, including the theory of linguistic universals. The general theory of language, together with typological linguistics, draws material for generalizations regarding the parametric characteristics of languages, simultaneously develops a methodology for linguistic search, as well as the necessary minimum of conceptual and categorical apparatus. Any linguistic research, including comparative research, has its initial precise choice of methodological orientation from form to content or from content to form. In recent decades, the content aspects of language have been preferred in linguistics. An approach to deciding the expediency of adopting a particular attitude in determining the status of morphological objectifications of deep semantic categories is becoming more differentiated.

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